

**TASK-BASED LEARNING EVALUATION INSTRUMENTS BY THE
DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITH NUANCES ISLAMIC EDUCATION
AT TPA (CHILDREN PARK) FOUNDATION PPAW KOLAKA**

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Abstract

This research is oriented towards learning evaluation instruments at TPA Al Mawaddah Warrahmah Kolaka. TPA Al Mawaddah Warrahmah Kolaka provides care and learning facilities for children aged 0-3 years. The concept of the resulting learning instrument is an evaluation instrument based on child development with the nuances of Islamic education. This instrument contains indicators of student development in terms of cognitive, language, motor and socioemotional abilities with age division: (1) 0-12 months, (2) 1-2 years, (3) 2-3 years, (4) 3 -4 years.

Keyword: *evaluation instrument, development of children, nuances islamic education*

Introduction

Children are the most beautiful gift from Allah SWT to their parents. Therefore, it is the duty of parents to prepare a person to become a generation of faith and piety and able to compete and face global challenges.

A child really needs knowledge as a provision in dealing with life. Because with science, children are able to adapt to the rotation of the wheel of time. However, as a generation of Muslims, the provision of knowledge must be based on religious education, because religious education is the foundation of children in navigating life and solving problems that they will face in the future. Of course, the preparation is done early on, even starting from the prenatal period of the baby in the womb.

Allah SWT. Tells about Luqman when educating his son: وَإِذْ قَالَ لُقْمَانُ لِابْنِهِ

وَهُوَ يَعِظُهُ يَا بُنَيَّ لَا تُشْرِكْ بِاللَّهِ إِنَّ الشِّرْكَ لَظُلْمٌ عَظِيمٌ

Artinya:

“And (remember) when Luqman said to his son, when he taught him: "O my son, do not associate partners with Allah". (QS. Luqman :13).

The verse above is one of the views that in the learning process it is very important to integrate with Islamic religious values. Because religious values can be a bulwark in facing the challenges of modernization that have a negative impact. Therefore, both the learning process of formal and non-formal educational institutions, must provide a learning process that is nuanced in Islamic education.

The PPAW Kolaka Foundation educational institution is an educational institution with the most complete levels of education both under the auspices of the Ministry of Education and Culture and the Ministry of Religion. The level of education under the auspices of the Ministry of Education and Culture begins with the KB (Play Group), TKIT, SMPIT, and SMAIT Al Mawar Kolaka levels. Meanwhile, the madrasah units under the auspices of the

Ministry of Religion consist of TPA (Child Care Park), RA (Raudhatul Athfal), MI, MTs and MA Pondok Pesantren Al Mwaddah Warrahmah Kolaka. In addition, this foundation has two universities, namely IAI Al Mawaddah Warrahmah Kolaka and IT Al Mawar Kolaka.

However, of all these work units, TPA is a unit whose learning outcomes are not formally accounted for. However, the quality of the unit must be maintained and accounted for. The quality assurance of learning from the unit should be included in a learning evaluation instrument. Therefore, the author made a study with the title "The Concept of Learning Evaluation Instruments Based on Child Development with Islamic Education Nuances in TPA (Child Care Park) at the PPAW Kolaka Foundation".

The formulation of the problem posed is how the Instrument for Evaluation of Child Development-Based Learning with the nuances of Islamic Education is presented at the TPA (Child Care Park) at the PPAW Kolaka Foundation". While the purpose of this study is to find out how the Concept of Learning Evaluation Instruments Based on Child Development with Islamic Education Nuances in TPA (Child Care Park) at PPAW Kolaka Foundation.

Explanation

Individual development is a pattern of movement or change that dynamically starts from conception or conception and continues throughout the human life cycle that occurs as a result of maturity and experience. Attitudes towards these developmental changes are influenced by individual appearance and behavior, cultural stereotypes, cultural values, role changes and personal experiences. One of the goals of this change is that individuals are able

to adapt to the environment so that both physically and psychologically in accordance with social expectations.

The changes in individual development are the result of interrelated biological, cognitive and socio-emotional processes. Biological processes include changes in the physical properties of individuals as they age will lead to maturity. For cognitive processes include changes in individual thinking, intelligence and language, while socio-emotional processes include changes in individual relationships with other people, as well as emotional and personality changes that accompany them.

According to Havighurst, each stage of individual development must be in line with the development of other aspects, namely physical, psychological and emotional, social and moral. There are two reasons why developmental tasks are important for education. First, it helps clarify the goals to be achieved by the school. Education can be understood as a community effort through schools, in helping individuals achieve certain developmental tasks. Second, this concept can be used as a time guide for carrying out educational efforts. If the individual has reached maturity, is ready to reach a certain task stage and is in accordance with the demands of society, it can be said that the time to teach the individual concerned has arrived. When teaching at the right time, optimal teaching results can be achieved.

Evaluation instrument is a tool used to measure the level of success of a program. An evaluation instrument that is not good will result in a poor evaluation result as well. For this reason, in developing an evaluation instrument, an evaluator must pay attention to things that affect the validity of the instrument and are related to the procedure for preparing the instrument. Therefore, in the preparation of children's development-based learning instruments with Islamic education nuances, they pay attention to the indicators of child development: (1) cognitive, (2) language, (3) motor, (4) socioemotional.

Result And Discussion

The Child Care Park (TPA) at the PPAW Kolaka Foundation provides care and learning facilities from 0 – 3 years. Therefore, this instrument was designed with 3 types of evaluation instruments based on child development with Islamic education nuances. The instrument consists of:

1. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (0-12 Months)
2. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (1 – 2 years)
3. Evaluation instruments based on child development with Islamic education nuances (2 – 3 years)
4. Instruments for evaluating child development based on Islamic education nuances (3 – 4 years)

The instrument for evaluating child development-based learning with Islamic education nuances at every level has the following indicators.

1. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (0-12 Months)

No	Dimensi Penilaian	Indikator	Kemampuan		Keterangan
			Ya	Tidak	
1	Motorik	0 – 6 bulan :			
		Mampu menggerakkan tangannya			
		Mampu Mendorong badannya keatas			
		Mampu memutar tubuhnya			
		Mampu memegang benda dengan kedua tangannya			
		Mampu tengkurap			
		7-12 bulan :			
		Mampu memegang benda dengan satu tangan			
		Mampu Merangkak			
		Mampu Menegakkan Punggung			
		Mampu mengambil benda yang menggantung meskipun belum bisa menggapainya			
		Mampu duduk lebih lama			
		Mampu duduk sendiri (Usia 9 - 12 bulan)			
Mampu berdiri dengan memegang sesuatu (Usia 9 -12 bulan)					
Mampu berjalan dengan bantuan					

		(9-12 bulan)			
		Mampu berjalan tanpa bantuan (10 -1 2 Bulan)			
		Koordinasi mata dengan tangan (mampu finger food secara mandiri) (8-12 bulan)			
		Mampu mengikuti gerakan shalat secara umum (12 bulan)			
		Mampu mengangkat tangan ketika berdoa (12 bulan)			
2	Bahasa	Komunikasi melalui ekspresi wajah Tersenyum ketika merasa bahagia dan menangis ketika merasa tidak nyaman			
		Memahami larangan jangan			
		Ucapan sederhana "mama" dan "papa" Mampu mengenal suara orang tuanya			
3	Sosioemosional	Menolak ketika tidak menyukai			
		Tersenyum kepada orang asing yang mengajak bermain atau berbicara kepadanya			
		Merasa cemas ketika orang baru mendekatinya			
		Menangis jika akan meninggalkan orang tuanya			
		Mengikuti orang disekitarnya ketika bertepuk tangan			

		Melambatkan tangan ketika berpisah			
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2. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (1-2 Years)

No	Dimensi Penilaian	Indikator	Kemampuan		Keterangan
			Ya	Tidak	
1	Kognitif	Menunjuk benda yang diinginkan			
		Memberikan respon terhadap pertanyaan sederhana yang diberikan			
		Mengidentifikasi nama beberapa benda yang ada disekitarnya minimal 10 benda			
		Mampu mengidentifikasi hewan yang pernah diajarkan			
		Mampu mengidentifikasi anggota tubuh			
		Mampu menyebutkan minimal 10 huruf hijaiyyah			
2	Motorik	Mampu memegang benda kecil seperti sereal			
		Berdiri sendiri			
		Mampu berjalan sendiri			
		Mengangkat tangan ketika berdoa			
3	Bahasa	Menirukan bahasa orang dewasa			

		yang biasa didengarnya			
		Berbicara dengan kalimat 2 - 3 kata			
4	Sosioemosional	Melambaikan tangan ketika berpisah dengan senyuman			
		Mampu menolak sesuatu jika merasa tidak nyaman			

3. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (2-3 Months)

No	Dimensi Penilaian	Indikator	Kemampuan		Keterangan
			Ya	Tidak	
1	Kognitif	Menyelesaikan puzzle sederhana			
		Mengingat apa yang terjadi satu hari yang lalu			
		Menghitung sampai 5			
		Mencocokkan benda			
		Mengidentifikasi bentuk-bentuk dasar			
		Mengikuti perintah sederhana			
		Fokus memperhatikan 3-5 menit			
		Mampu menghafalkan dua kalimat syahadat			
		Mampu membaca doa sebelum belajar			
		Mengenal semua huruf			

		hijaiyyah			
		Menyayikan asmaul husna			
2	Motorik Kasar	Mampu berlari tanpa sering terjatuh			
		Mampu berlari menghindari hambatan			
		Mampu berdiri seimbang dengan satu kaki durasi pendek			
		Mampu naik turun tangga dengan kaki kiri dan kanan			
		Mampu mendarat melompat dengan dua kaki			
		Mampu melompat 15 centimeter			
		Mampu melempar bola diatas kepala			
		Mampu menangkap bola			
		Mampu menendang bola besar			
		Mampu mengayuh sepeda kecil roda tiga dan roda empat			
		Berjalan dalam garis lurus dan jinjit			
		Mampu mengikuti gerakan shalat			
3	Motorik halus	Mencuci dan lap tangan sendiri			
		Menggunakan sendok dan garpu sendiri			
		Mampu menyendok kuah dari			

		mangkok			
		Mampu membawah wadah berisi air tanpa menumpahkan			
		Mampu memakai sandal sendiri			
		Mampu membolak-balik buku			
		Mampu mewarnai walau keluar garis			
		Mampu membuat menara 9 balok			
3	Bahasa	Mengetahui namanya			
		Mampu menjawab singkat untuk pertanyaan sederhana			
		Bercerita			
		Mampu bertanya secara sederhana			
4	Sosioemosional	Mampu mengekspresikan perasaannya			
		Membantu teman			
		Berbagi mainan dengan teman			
		Berbagi makanan dengan taman			
		Mampu mengikuti shalat berjamaah			
		Mengucapkan salam ketika masuk rumah			

4. Evaluation instrument based on child development with Islamic education nuances (3-4 Months)

No	Dimensi Penilaian	Indikator	Kemampuan		Keterangan
			Ya	Tidak	
1	Kognitif	Mampu bercerita cerita yang telah diceritakan sebelumnya			
		Mengurutkan objek			
		Menentukan persamaan warna			
		Membandingkan ukuran sebuah benda			
		Dapat melaksanakan perintah sederhana			
		Menghafal 2 doa harian			
		Mampu menyanyikan asmaul husna			
2	Motorik kasar	Mampu berlari tanpa sering terjatuh			
		Mampu berlari menghindari hambatan			
		Mampu berdiri seimbang dengan satu kaki durasi pendek			
		Mampu naik turun tangga dengan kaki kiri dan kanan			
		Mampu mendarat melompat dengan dua kaki			
		Mampu melompat 15 centimeter			
		Mampu melempar bola diatas kepala			
		Mampu menangkap bola			
Mampu menendang bola besar					

		Mampu mengayuh sepeda kecil roda tiga dan roda empat			
		Berjalan dalam garis lurus dan jinjit			
		Berjalan maju mundur			
		Membungkuk tanpa jatuh			
	Motorik halus	Memakai dan melepas baju sendiri			
		Menggunakan gunting mainan			
		Menggambar lingkaran dan kotak			
		Mennggambar 2-4 bagian tubuh			
		Menulis beberapa huruf kapital			
		Membangun menara dengan 4 blok			
		Memutar gagang pintu			
		Membuka dan menutup toples atau wadah			
3	Bahasa	Belajar toilet training			
		Mengetahui beberapa jenis suara binatang			
		Menirukan beberapa jenis suara			
		Mampu bertanya kepada orang lain			
4	Sosioemosional	Memilih teman dalam bermain			
		Mengurangi tingkah laku bermusuhan			
		Mengobrol bersama teman sambil bermain			

		Mengekspresikan emosi			
		Mampu sabar dalam mencapai keinginannya			
		Menunjukkan kebanggaan terhadap keberhasilannya			
		Memecahkan masalah dengan teman sekelas melalui negoisasi			
		Memiliki rasa ingin tahu yang tinggi			
		Membuat sesuatu dengan imajinasi			

Conclusion

The concept of the resulting learning instrument is an evaluation instrument based on child development with the nuances of Islamic education. This instrument contains indicators of student development in terms of cognitive, language, motor and socioemotional abilities with age division: (1) 0-12 months, (2) 1-2 years, (3) 2-3 years, (4) 3 -4 years.

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